

Foundation Models for Telecom: Paving the Way for Self-Built Networks

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White Paper: Foundation Models for Telecom Paving The Way for Self-Built Networks

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**WIRELESS WORLD
RESEARCH FORUM**

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

Foundation Models for Telecom: paving
the way for self-built networks.

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The biggest lesson that can be read from 70 years of AI research is that **general methods that leverage computation are ultimately the most effective**, and by a large margin.

Rich Sutton, [The Bitter Lesson](#)

The Extreme-scale Era of Machine Learning

Extreme-scale Models for NLP

Go Big to Boost The Performance

Over the last four years, the size of state-of-the-art language models has doubled every 3-4 months

Extra-scale language models are greedy in data

Model	Size (# Parameters)	Training Tokens
LaMDA (Thoppilan et al., 2022)	137 Billion	168 Billion
GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020)	175 Billion	300 Billion
Jurassic (Lieber et al., 2021)	178 Billion	300 Billion
Gopher (Rae et al., 2021)	280 Billion	300 Billion
MT-NLG 530B (Smith et al., 2022)	530 Billion	270 Billion

Most models are trained for approximately 300 billion tokens

Performance depends strongly on scale, weakly on model shape

Extreme-scale Language Models

Scaling Laws

Kaplan et al. : Language modeling performance improves smoothly as we increase the model size, dataset size, and amount of compute used for training. For optimal performance, all three factors must be scaled up in tandem. Empirical performance has a power-law relationship with each individual factor when not bottlenecked by the other two.

What Is LLM and How It Works

- LLM stands for **Large Language Models**
- It is a **type of machine learning model** that uses **natural language** input and output
- LLMs are **trained on large amounts of text data** and **can perform a variety of end-tasks** related to natural language processing (NLP)
- The models use techniques like **neural networks**, **specifically transformer-based models** like BERT, GPT, T5... which have proven to be very effective in natural language tasks

LLM: Multi-Task Models

At Scale, Unique Capabilities Arise Few-Shot Learning

Power of extra-scale language models, **No need to fine-tuning** : Larger models can deal with unseen tasks on-the-fly

Language Models are Few-Shot Learners, Brown et al

Few-shot

In addition to the task description, the model sees a few examples of the task. No gradient updates are performed.

- Zero-shot : No example is provided, a description of the task only
- One-shot : One example is provided
- Few-shot : >1 examples are provided

What LLM Can Do

Content creation

Text / Code

Idea generation

Text writing (book, training, course, plan...)

Copywriting (emails, ads, blog posts...)

Code writing (website, app...)

Visuals / Sounds

Image generation (text-to-image)

Video generation (text-to-video)

Voice generation (text-to-voice)

Game design (AR, 3D design...)

Content curation and analysis

Rewrite / Summarize

Text summary

Video summary

Audio transcript

Language translation

Information clustering / formatting

Extract

Information retrieval

Web search / Benchmarking

Q&A

Analyze

Data analytics and forecast

Visual analytics

Sentiment / Intent recognition (ex. Fraud)

Task automation

Chatbot / Virtual assistant

Scheduling (meetings, tasks...)

Text editing (spell check, paraphrasing)

Visuals editing (video cutting, image editing...)

Data cleansing

Code auditing

Robot control

From SON to Cognitive Networks ..

Self-organizing network (SON) represents an intelligent and adaptive framework that empowers communication networks to become more autonomous, and responsive to the dynamic demands of modern users and applications.

Self-Evolving Networks ..

Future networks will be able to self-learn and self-improve → Self-Synthesizing Networks

Self-Evolving Networks ..

Large Language Models (LLMs) are the way forward ..

Why LLM Can be attractive for Telecom?

Are we constrained by the language??

Telecom Use Case

Fine-tuning LLM with Telecom Knowledge

Motivation:

Pre-trained large language models (LLMs) lack knowledge of Telecom.

Goals:

Build general-purpose Telecom-oriented LLM:

- Classify, summarize, generate, query telecom text from research paper, technical patent, standard specifications, and so on.
- Automate process of standardization, patenting, facilitate cooperation between researchers, standard delegates and engineers.
- Break down High-level intent into executable actions/tasks/plans.
- Generate pseudo codes/commands to implement new standard, features in wireless network.

SoTA LLM performance on TeleQnA

Foundation Model for Wireless Communications

Understanding Telecom Language Through Large Language Models

- A stepping-stone towards realizing intent-driven and self-evolving wireless networks from Telecom languages: **using LLM to break down natural language intents to tasks within specific network functions.**
- Adapting pretrained generative models, including BERT, DistilBERT, RoBERTa, GPT-2 models to Telecom language.
- The framework demonstrates the applicability of adapting pretrained generative models into the network devices, where the distilled fine-tuned model showed **accurate classification performance with smaller model size.**

Classifying Working Groups of 3GPP Language

Models	DistilBERT	BERT	RoBERTa	GPT-2
Accuracy (%)	84	84.3	84.5	83.5
Parameters (M)	66	117	125	124

In LTE system, 16-bit CRC on PDCCH channels is reserved for error detection only to ensure a 10^{-5} DCI FAR. In a CA-SCL decoding implementation, this CRC or a part of it, is to be checked more than once to select one from the L survival paths, hence the CRC is also used for error correction. In CA-SCL decoder, the 16-bit CRC would be checked L times, which would compromise its FAR performance. Evaluations of the BLER performance [5-10] have shown a FAR loss due to the CA-SCL decoder. This conclusion is valid regardless of how to deploy the CRC bits, either consecutively appended to the information bits or distributed.

Observation-1: A CA-SCL decoder brings FAR penalty.

3.1 PC-Polar

A PC-Polar allows a PC-SCL decoder that needs no CRC bits but some parity-check frozen bits for SCL decoder. These PC frozen bits are carefully chosen to take some relatively reliable positions, over which simple parity-check functions/equations are implemented. PC-SCL decoder can use them to prune the SCL tree at an earlier stage than CA-SCL decoder without impact on the FAR performance which is guaranteed by the reserved CRC bits.

Observation-2: A PC-SCL decoder has no FAR penalty.

3.2 Longer-CRC polar

Large Language Model

Tdoc Preprocessing

3GPP TSG RAN WG1 Meeting #97
Reno, USA, May 13th – 17th, 2019

R1-1906313 Document # (contains group)

Source: CATT
Title: Discussion of NR-U initial access procedures
Agenda Item: 7.2.2.2.2
Document for: Discussion and Decision

1 Introduction

The following agreements were made on the NR-U initial access and mobility procedures in RAN1#96bis[1]:

Agreement

The maximum DRS transmission window duration is 5 ms.

- The maximum number of candidate SSB positions within a DRS transmission window, Y , is selected as $Y = 10$ for 15 kHz SCS and $Y = 20$ for 30 kHz SCS.
 - Note: The number of starting points for DRS transmissions with the 5 ms window that can use a Cat. 2 LBT is to be discussed further as part of channel access discussions.
- FFS: If the DRS transmission window is configurable, and if yes, how to configure and indicate the window, including the range of configurable values.

Agreement

For a given cell, the UE may assume that the PBCH DMRS sequence index is the same for SS/PBCH blocks that are transmitted at the same candidate positions across DRS transmission windows.

Agreement

UE determines serving cell timing from the detected SSB candidate position, where the SSB candidate positions within the DRS transmission window are indexed from $0, \dots, Y-1$ ($Y = 10$ for 15 kHz SCS and $Y = 20$ for 30 kHz SCS).

- Remove titles, heads, references
- Remove tables, figures and equations
- Remove special characters...

Understanding Telecom Language through Large Language Models

- **Aim:** Allow generative models to identify a particular technical text, related to 3GPP cellular architecture category: RAN, SA, or CT.
- Create an annotated large Telecom datasets from 3GPP technical specification: RF spectrum usage, network architecture, radio interface protocols, signaling procedures, mobility management, network architecture, system interfaces, etc.
- Fine-tune pre-trained generative models using Telecom language → 3GPP Tdocs text classification.

RAN	SA	CT	Accuracy (%)
1	1	1	98.05
1,2,3	None	None	88.90
1,2,3	1	1	88.26
1,2,3,4	2,5	None	87.42
1,2,3	1,2,3	1,3,4	86.61
1,2,3,4	1,2,3,4	1,3,4,6	85.57
1,2,3,4,5	1,2,3,4,5,6	1,3,4,6	84.35

BERT classification accuracy on different WGs

Classification accuracy of different LLMs vs. portion of 3GPP files used for fine-tuning

LLM for Telecom

LLM Telecom: Wireless Sensing and Communication

LLM Telecom: Intelligent Sensing & Communication

LLM Telecom: Wireless Sensing and Communication

LLM for Wireless Imaging

- Conventional *wireless sensing* is performed through DL, which is performed in a supervised fashion, maps received wireless signals' characteristics into 2D images.
- Generative visual AI models**, like DALL-E, CLIP and VQGAN, and GPT Image, target to construct high-quality images from textual descriptions.
- Adopting visual large models at the Telecom domain → create high-resolution 3D visualization of the wireless environment using wireless data.
- Objective:** Develop foundation models that are capable of converting wireless signals to images [for improved contextual knowledge and enhanced communication schemes], and vice-versa.

LLM Telecom: Wireless Sensing and Communication

LLM for Wireless Beam Management

- Multi-modal transformer deep learning framework using camera, LiDAR, radar and GPS sensors for wireless mmWave beam prediction in V2X scenario. The solution is scalable to different modalities data and targeted tasks in wireless communications.
- Achieves overall prediction accuracy at 78.44%, with good generalization to different scenarios in day (1, 2), night (3, 4) and unseen scenario (1).

Multi-Modal Transformer Framework

Beam Prediction Accuracy (%)

Scenarios	Overall	Day 1 (unseen)	Day 2	Night 3	Night 4
Multi-Modal Transformer	78.44	72.98	78.52	84.62	84.33
Auto-Encoder	71.62	65.36	70.74	85.76	71.20

LLM Telecom: Wireless Sensing and Communication

LLM for FDD

Telecom for LLM

A possible example

From Connected Intelligence to Collective Intelligence

- **Collective Intelligence:** connecting multiple LLM agents to through wireless networks to reason on complicated tasks
 - **Generative agent** leverage LLM to break down higher-level prompts into lower level tasks, take actions and plan new tasks until the task goals are accomplished.
 - **On-device LLM** reflect abstractions of observations, plan sequences of consistent actions over time, retrieve relevant and priority actions to execute.
 - **Multiple LLM agents** exchange knowledge (semantics) to enable emergent intelligence and collectively solve complicated tasks
- **Self-design Network:** LLM breaks down human intents into actionable network configurations and policies, signaling each agents with protocol languages to complete the goal.

Multi-Agent LLMs Network: Technologies

- Multi-agent LLM Planning and Reasoning
 - Create actionable tasks collaboratively by LLMs over time to achieve a specific goal
 - Chain / tree of thought prompt LLM with intermediate reasoning steps to solve problems
 - Further research on multi-agent collaborative planning, and deterministic output from LLM
- Multi-agent LLM Game and Reinforcement Learning
 - Game theory could model multi-agent LLM interactions and analyze their behavior
 - Balance between network collaborative goals and agent's independent goals
 - Multi-agent RL to learn optimal collaboration policies and communication protocols
- Semantic Information and Communication
 - Multi-agent LLMs transfer, memorize, encode task specific knowledge in network
 - Model multi-modal raw data in a concept space to reduce on-device LLM cost
 - Flexible transfer between low and high-order semantics for short and long-term tasks

Multi-Agent LLMs Network: Applications

- Intent-driven Network Automation
 - LLM extends intent-driven network concept to a general purpose self-designed network
 - Deconstruct high-level human intents to network entities and layers configurations
 - On-device LLMs collaboratively optimize network from perceived wireless environment
 - Learn communication protocol for emerging applications to power self-evolving network
- Collaborative Autonomous Agents
 - LLMs power various wireless devices, i.e., vehicles, machines, sensors, mobile terminals
 - Connecting multiple LLM agents to perform collaborative control, query, inference, etc.
 - Emerging protocol learning to improve multi-agent communication efficiency and reliability

Case Study: Multi-Agent LLM Games

- Evaluate the capability of multiple on-device LLMs in solving a wireless communication problem
 - Goal: reduce network energy consumption while keeping transmission rate at each user
 - Multiple GPT-4 instances play games through prompts with the information of radio environment and action history
 - In round 2 all 4 agents achieve 5% energy reduction target with transmission rate above 5 kbps as specified
- Further work needed to adapt LLM on wireless domain knowledge for fully autonomous reasoning

Scenario: Consider the downlink channel with one base station and k users. The noise level is the same for all users and equals to n dB. The bandwidth is b kHz. The channel gain vector is g . The initial transmission power vector is p .

Game rule: in each round, each user should choose its power so that its transmission rate is no less than its minimum rate and the difference (always non-negative) of its current transmitting power w.r.t. its initial power is minimized. There are x rounds for each user to choose the transmitting power.

Network goal: reduce the total power by Δp W at least.

User goal: minimum transmission rate : r kbps.

It is currently round x_t . You are user k_i .
 In the last round, transmitting power including yourself is: p'
 When you calculate your transmission rate, you can use $r_k = B \log(1 + \frac{p_k g_k}{n^2 + \sum_{i \neq k} p_i g_i})$
 How will you choose your transmitting power in next round?
 Your reply should be like 'my transmitting power is ... W'

The Way Forward ..

What are the challenges & limitations?

Do current architectures perform reliably when Telecom data is used?

From where we can get the data?

Computing & memory resources at the edge – models compression

Distributed GPT

Can agents self-replicate?

Thank you

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Well ... We are!!

Thank you